

Supplementary Material: Educational Backgrounds of Survey Participants

Table 1 lists all participants' post-secondary education background, i.e., high school diplomas or equivalents are not included. Since the details could lead to participants being identified, their post-secondary education backgrounds are not listed in detail, but categorized based on Statistics Canada's classification system [1, 2]. The "Unknown" column is for when participants responded that they have a type of degree but did not specify the field and/or status, or if the type of degree is not listed within the classification system used [1, 2] and hence cannot be categorized. Each value denotes the level of study (e.g., undergraduate degree denoted as U (Table 2)) and also its status (e.g., *IP* for in progress (Table 2), if the information is given by the participants. Participant 24's row has a "?" as they only noted the field of the degree, but not its level or status.

Take note that education in SE or CS are not separated as its own category, but grouped as part of the M&CS column, which also includes areas like statistics and actuarial science. As such, credentials that participants specified as SE or CS are bolded in Table 1. The survey did not include any question for participants to inform us whether they were recruited through the mailing list in the authors' institution, or through snowball sampling. And while there is no explicit way to differentiate between the participants recruited through each method, only graduate students who are in the midst of completing their Master's or PhD in Computer Science in the authors' institution received the survey recruitment email through the mailing list. As such, assuming participants reported their education background truthfully, from Table 1, it is possible that a maximum of 11 participants (P7,11,15,17,19,24,27,29,40, and possibly P26 and 43) were recruited from the mailing list, with the others very possibly recruited from snowball sampling instead.

Some participants also included the name of the post-secondary institutions from which they attained their credentials, including those in the United States of America, Canada, Brazil and the United Kingdom.

Table 1: Survey participants' post-secondary education background. Please refer to Table 2 for the meaning of abbreviations used.

ID	STEM			BHAASE							Unknown	
	Sc	Eng	M&CS	B&A	A&H	SS	Legal	Hlth	Edu	Tr		
1			TP	U, PTP								
2				UC	MC, DNC							
3		UC										
4			TP	U, TP			U, PTP					
5	U											
6			TP					TP	U			
7		UC	M+DIP									
8		UC										
9			U									
10												UIP
11		UC	MIP									
12									UC			
13			UC, MC, DC					UC, MC				
14		UC										
15			UC, MC, DIP	MC								
16			PTPC		UC							
17		UC	MC, DIP									
18												UNC
19		U, M	M, D									
20	UC											
21		U	M									
22		U										
23			MC						UC			
24			?									
25				UC		UNC						
26												UC, MC, DIP
27			UC, MC, DIP									
28												UC
29			UC, MIP									
30					MC	UC						
31					U							
32		UC	TPC								TPC	
33				M	U							
34												UNC
35						UC					MC	
36			M	MC								
37				UC								
38	MC	UC										
39				M								
40			MC, DIP	UC								
41					UC, MC							
42	TP											U
43			UC	MC								MIP
44		U										
45												UNC
46						UNC						TP

Table 2: Abbreviations used in Table 1 and their meanings.

Abbrev.	Full name
STEM Fields	
Sc	Science and science technology
Eng	Engineering and engineering technology
M&CS	Mathematics and computer and information sciences
BHASE Fields	
B&A	Business and administration
A&H	Arts and humanities
SS	Social and behavioral sciences
Legal	Legal professions and studies
Hlth	Health care
Edu	Education and teaching
Tr	Trades, services, natural resources and conservation
Program Type	
TP	Career, technical or professional training program
PTP	Post career, technical or professional training program
U	Undergraduate program
PB	Post-baccalaureate non-graduate program
M	Master's-level program
D	Doctoral-level program
M+D	Joint Master's and Doctoral-level program
Program Status	
<i>C</i>	Program completed
<i>NC</i>	Program not completed
<i>IP</i>	Program in progress

References

- [1] Canada, S.: Variant of the Classification of Instructional Programs (CIP) Canada 2021 Version 1.0 for Science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) and Business, humanities, health, arts, social science and education (BHASE) groupings (2022). <https://www23.statcan.gc.ca/imdb/p3VD.pl?Function=getVD&TVD=1486451>
- [2] Canada, S.: Classification of programs and credentials (2019). <https://www23.statcan.gc.ca/imdb/p3VD.pl?Function=getVD&TVD=1252482&CVD=1252483&CLV=0&MLV=2&D=1>